

1 Rmi1 connects genomic instability with transcriptional noise through Xist.

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7 We studied the transcriptional properties of Rmi1, a molecule associated with genomic instability. Rmi1
8 was widely expressed in human cancer.

9 Co-regulation of Rmi1 with Rb1 suggested Rmi1 was connected to tumor suppression. Accordingly, Rmi1
10 was activated in intraepithelial neoplasia in humans in vivo. Rmi1 was expressed in a p53 status
11 dependent fashion in the tumors of humans with lung cancer. Rmi1 could be controlled by transgenic
12 expression of Xist, and was co-regulated with components of the Xist RNP, including KHDRBS1 and ILF2.
13 Rmi1 co-regulation with DNMT1, PARP1 and TET2 indicated Rmi1 function was associated with repair
14 and methylation of the DNA. The function of Rmi1 in genomic instability, the fact that Rmi1 is a marker of
15 genomic instability, Rmi1 co-regulation with tumor suppression, activation of Rmi1 in transformation and
16 human cancer, and control of Rmi by Xist is indicative of a function for Xist and the imprinting system in
17 establishing homeostatic transcriptional control through regulation or balancing of “transcriptional noise”
18 which becomes dysregulated in cancer.
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